

EXCELERATE Deliverable 9.4

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2. Executive Summary

The primary goal of EXCELERATE WP9 is to build and enhance the infrastructure to enable sharing of controlled access human genetic and phenotype data across Europe. Molecular medicine is undergoing a paradigm shift as advances in high throughput DNA sequencing technology make it feasible to use genomics in clinical practice. One of the core goals for the ELIXIR Human data platform is to enable sharing of human genetic data for research, acknowledging that in the future much of this data is likely to come from healthcare initiatives. In the near future, we expect that the majority of genomic data for research will come from secondary reuse of healthcare data. However, healthcare is considered a national competence and data generated is unlikely to be shared as freely as research data. WP9 of EXCELERATE aims to build the fundamental building blocks needed to establish a federated infrastructure across the ELIXIR network for human data sharing.

The European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) is an ELIXIR core data resource for permanent secure archiving and sharing of all types of potentially identifiable genetic and phenotypic data resulting from biomedical research projects. The EGA has been

operational since 2008 at EMBL-EBI, and in 2012 became a federated resource with the CRG, Barcelona.

In this deliverable, we report on the development of two key components in support of the establishment of an ELIXIR wide federated human data infrastructure:

1. Create robust and standardised data access APIs that support new data access patterns such as real-time integration into downstream resource portals, cloud platforms, and local repositories.
2. Robust systems for the management of data access rights across the ELIXIR resources.

3. Impact

EGA data access API metrics:

- Max download volume in a single month was 494TB
- 12mth period was 3.93PB, and 10.33PB distributed in total
- 2432 distinct users have used the EGA Data Access API v2 to access 631,112 distinct files

Between June-July 2018, the *htsget* paper¹ was mentioned by:

- 5 news outlets
- 1 blog
- 138 twitter users

Workshop talks:

- "Genomic data sharing challenges and solutions", Inaugural meeting of the Nordic Alliance for Sequencing and Personalized Medicine. November 2017. Oslo.
- "European Genome-phenome Archive: Introduction and future", American society for human genetics meeting. November 2017. Orlando.
- "Towards a federated network of nodes hosting human genetic and phenotype data". 1st European Alliance for Personalised Medicine Congress, Nov 2017. Belfast.
- "Towards a federated network of nodes hosting human genetic and phenotype data", "Omics in Medical Research" to be organized by TMF (a Federal Ministry of Education and Research-funded umbrella organization for networked medical research in Germany). Dec 2017. Berlin.
- "Genomic data access through European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA): Access models and governance considerations". Inter-university Course on Clinical and Research Genomic Data Sharing and Access, Leuven Institute for Human Genomics and Society, Aug 2017. Leuven.

¹ Kelleher *et al.* (2018) *Bioinformatics*, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty492>

4. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	To upgrade and make more portable -omics data collection and submission tools utilizing the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) as the core of an ELIXIR community secure data sharing network for - omics data.		x
2	To enable value-added services at project specific, regional, or national resources by establishing ELIXIR-wide community facing tools that allow local resource owners and developers to add value to their systems through data and metadata services from the EGA.	x	
3	To extend and generalise the system of access authorization management and high volume secure data transfer developed in the EGA project to address the secure data access needs across ELIXIR resources and open new modes of secure data access such as through public and private clouds.	x	

5. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

6. Adjustments made

None.

7. Background information

Background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	9	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Use Case D: ELIXIR framework for secure archiving, dissemination and analysis of human access-controlled data		
Lead	1 - EMBL-EBI		

Participant number and person months per participant

1 - EMBL (34 PM), 5 - UTARTU (16 PM), 6 - NBIC (0 PM), UMCG (LTP to NBIC) (5 PM), 8 - CRG (22.3 PM), 14 - UPF (23.5 PM), 20 - CSC (24 PM), THL (LTP to CSC) (3 PM), 24 - UiO (6 PM), 45 - UU (2 PM), SU (LTP to UU) (4 PM).

Objectives

This Work Package has three main objectives:

To upgrade and make more portable -omics data collection and submission tools utilizing the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) as the core of an ELIXIR community secure data sharing network for -omics data. Tools developed here will support submission of all types of -omics data from human samples consented for biomedical research from disease consortia such as International Cancer Genome Consortium (ICGC), Rare Diseases (Rd-Connect), national cohorts, and biobanks. Emphasis is given to supporting investigator and locally driven research projects with human data consented for biomedical research. To enable these projects, the data submission tool chain will be made more portable and user-friendly with the goal of distributing a common toolset “in-a-box” to enable local and national groups to collect -omics data and meta data in a distributed manner which is consistent across European groups through ELIXIR coordination.

To enable value-added services at project specific, regional, or national resources by establishing ELIXIR-wide community facing tools that allow local resource owners and developers to add value to their systems through data and metadata services from the EGA. For example, local research projects would be enabled to make their data discoverable and searchable, and linked with available -omics data from various sources, by leveraging stable unique EGA identifiers. Further, locally developed project specific data portals will be enabled through defined standard APIs using real time secure data links which allow -omics big data archived in the EGA to be presented in combination with biobanks or cohort data.

To extend and generalise the system of access authorization management and high volume secure data transfer developed in the EGA project to address the secure data access needs across ELIXIR resources and open new modes of secure data access such as through public and private clouds. For example, a trusted ELIXIR Cloud service can receive local copies of selected datasets through a secure data mirroring system and provide access to data and compute to those users that already have data access permissions available from appropriate Data Access Committees stored in the EGA system. The WP will partner first with 2-4 large

resource owners to gain the required expertise, document the process in multiple ELIXIR member states and finally to propose a way to scale up these services to match wider European requirements. This WP will also be used to drive creation of the ELSI framework that supports the workflow (WP12).

Work Package Leads: Thomas Keane, EMBL-EBI (since 1/3/2017); Jordi Rambla, CRG EGA (since 1/3/2017); Justin Paschall, EBI (up to 1/3/2017); Arcadi Navarro, ES (up to 1/3/2017)

Description of work and role of partners

WP9 - Use Case D: ELIXIR framework for secure archiving, dissemination and analysis of human access-controlled data [Months: 1-48]

EMBL, UTARTU, NBIC, CRG, UPF, CSC, UiO, UU

This WP delivers the core ELIXIR workflow for long term archive and re-use of human data consented for biomedical research requiring access-control based on a data access agreement and approval process. The workflow supports data submitters and ELIXIR Node coordination on data deposition into the EGA archive in a manner that will maintain data ownership in the hands of the original research data owner, enable data release to authorised individual users from the archive and to partner with downstream secure ELIXIR data analysis platforms. This workflow and supporting infrastructure will allow the data owners to focus on their unique areas of data generation and analysis expertise while being able to rely on EGA and the ELIXIR infrastructure for their common –omics big data storage, coordination and distribution needs under appropriate legal frameworks. The work described here will leverage the work of other ELIXIR-EXCELERATE Work Packages, for example WP10 to scale each service structure to cover all ELIXIR Nodes and with WP4 for technical service support, and relies on WP12 to establish the necessary legal framework that supports workflows.

The Workflow can be summarized as:

1. Data preparation, validation, and submission to the EGA making use of common supporting tools and data models (e.g. through Node data Network, WP10). Focus on providing software tools and remote APIs enabling local leadership and customisation within context of specific projects, supported by common ELIXIR coordinated tools and data models.
2. Bidirectional linking and secure data streaming between -omics data archived in EGA and local repositories or data portals that hold further information about the project and samples.
3. Management of user access-rights for release of archived data to authorized researchers under Data Access

Agreements using ELIXIR tools, such as the REMS (WP4), that allow resource owners to manage data access rights.

4. Expanded access through ELIXIR partner secure clouds that can host EGA datasets, requiring the provision of metadata and authorization APIs
5. Data synchronization between the main EGA archive and authorized project specific resources and access points, such as compute clouds.

Task 9.1: Enhanced secure data submission tools. (49PM)

This task will update the existing EGA submission tools and documentation to facilitate large-scale data submissions operations, emphasizing local leadership and customization within a common framework.

Partners: ES, EMBL-EBI, FI

Subtask 9.1.1: Support for large scale submission of -omics data and sample metadata to the EGA. (30PM)

Support for large-scale submission of -omics data and sample metadata to the EGA through improved online tools, automated verification, and tools for the application of standard vocabularies to phenotype collection. These tools will make use of table “spread-sheet” based views of data for submitters less comfortable with technologies such as XML. Further tools and reports supporting global EGA stable identifier mappings will allow easier integration with local identifiers, in support of federated global tracking of submitted samples and their derived -omics data.

Subtask 9.1.2: Portable submission toolkit. (21PM)

This task is composed of data format definitions and software components, a “mini-EGA in-a-box” will allow increased local control and coordination of data collection, and allow early validation of standardized data and metadata formats.

This implementation provides the practical means for distributed projects to collect access-controlled human biomedical data in a manner that maintains a coordinated data model and dataset registry, enabling federated and a centralized single-point of discovery and access.

Task 9.2: Integrating centralized and distributed projects through transparent access to secure data: enabling local projects within a European wide framework. (40PM)

This task will enable local projects, such as study-specific data portals, local cohort resources, and national bioinformatics hubs by providing developer level APIs and services such that local efforts can efficiently build customized project branded solutions which make use of underlying ELIXIR and EGA tools and data archives.

Partners: ES, EMBL-EBI, FI, EE, NL, NO, SE

Subtask 9.2.1: Support secure integration of EGA data to downstream project client websites. (10PM)

Support secure integration of EGA data and metadata to downstream project client websites by providing new EGA programmatic interfaces that support standardized REST calls and provides results in ELIXIR endorsed formats (WP3 and WP6).

Subtask 9.2.2: Access management workflow support. (10PM)

Support access management workflows by data access committees through ELIXIR for EGA and other projects through developing applications of the Resource Entitlement Management Systems (REMS) expanding on an existing pilot project. This effort is focused on providing tools to delegate management to local projects and ELIXIR Nodes through new administrative roles.

Subtask 9.2.3: ELIXIR and EGA access integration. (20PM)

Specific efforts supporting controlled access-omics data infrastructure for use of partner national cohort studies in terms of submission, permissions management, and local and customized presentation of data under the cohort branding. Services will be tailored to respect the unique policy and data protection requirements of national cohorts, allowing single point of request and download from cohort branded web-pages. Support will be provided for distributed local hosting of datasets, within a common ELIXIR framework, where restrictions exist on the movement or hosting of data based on national borders.

Task 9.3: Federated authentication, large scale data management, and secure clouds in practice. (38PM)

This task is closely linked to the technically focused WP4 that provide the technical solutions required to deliver the outcomes of Task 9.1 and 9.2. In this task, technical components, including high volume secure data transfer and authentication and authorization management, are brought together to make -omics data from EGA and phenotypic data from cohort studies available for secure download, remote API access or from within public or private Cloud-based secure analysis environments. Cloud-based access to the EGA ecosystem provides a new access mode meeting a significant user need from research groups with limited local resources for compute and large-scale reference data storage.

Partners: EMBL-EBI, ES, FI, EE

Subtask 9.3.1: Large scale data mirroring support. (12PM)

Support for automated large scale data mirroring from the EGA archive to the authorized ELIXIR partner local services and cloud compute or HPC providers. This process instantiates concrete data flows based on data transfer technologies in WP4 to track domain specific files, versions of files, confirms transfer success, and tracks files available in different locations. Generic interfaces should provide transparent access to multiple underlying transfer and storage modules (e.g. gridFTP/irods/object store etc.)

Subtask 9.3.2: EGA data access authorization integration. (12PM)

Integrate EGA data access authorizations to local project data portals and Cloud access providers. This is a new service that allows authorized third-party services to programmatically check compliance with the current user data access authorizations from the ELIXIR coordinated repositories such as the EGA database each time user accesses

a file in the cloud or other remote service. A first planned project using EGA data within the private, secure, cloud at CSC in Finland will provide our reference implementation.

Subtask 9.3.3: Data access APIs. (14PM)

Develop and implement standard data access APIs to be used for inter and intra cloud communication and for secure remote REST API access in coordination with the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH).

For tasks 1-3 we expect to list a number of updates to the submission tools while we work with the first 2-4 chosen resources. These updates will be prioritised in the scope of this WP. WP4 will provide AAI support for WP 9, and vice versa WP9 will work with WP4 to set the requirements for ELIXIR AAI services. WP9 needs to information on service component availability and this information is expected to be available from technical services registry such as cloud resource allocation, valid EGA data access authorizations, and file mirroring status if data are not yet ready to be used in the cloud. WP12 will Create a set of Legal Frameworks for ELIXIR-related operations that will be integrated within WP9 with the technical solutions devised for particular EGA needs.

8. Appendix 1: Implementation of cloud access and secure user and data management

Introduction

The goal of EXCELERATE WP9 is to deliver the core ELIXIR workflow for long term archive and re-use of human data consented for biomedical research across Europe. Deliverable 9.1 established the requirements analysis for the core components and processes (Data Transfer API, Metadata API, Submissions API, Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure, Permissions API, Portals, Local EGA, Cloud). This deliverable addresses two specific challenges in WP9:

1. Create robust data access APIs that support new patterns of sharing human data to enable integration and customisation by downstream resource portals, cloud platforms, and local repositories.
2. Management of user access-rights to human genetic datasets supported by ELIXIR infrastructure.

Challenge 1 was addressed by the expansion of the EGA Data Access API through the development of the htsgget API, a GA4GH standardised interface for requesting and accessing human genetic data by genomic locus, and the development of the EGA FUSE virtual filesystem. The new Data Access API has been used by the RD-Connect platform to enable users to inspect the raw data (sequencing reads) supporting genetic variants. The remote FUSE filesystem will form an essential component to enable Cloud access and local caches of EGA data, which has been demonstrated with partner CSC (ELIXIR-Finland).

The European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA) is an ELIXIR core data resource for permanent secure archiving and sharing of all types of potentially identifiable genetic and phenotypic data resulting from biomedical research projects. Since 2012, it is a federated resource that is jointly managed by EMBL-EBI and CRG, Barcelona. Its aim is to provide access to data, to foster data re-use, to enable reproducibility and to speed up biomedical and translational research in line with the 'FAIR' (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. Access to EGA data must be approved by a Data Access Committee (DAC) and data must be appropriately consented for sharing.

Human research data is submitted to the EGA with appropriate metadata, archived and accessioned, and distributed by to authorised users. This gives users limited options to access slices or subsets of the data prior to full download. Prior to the EXCELERATE project, the primary mode of accessing controlled access human EGA data in Europe was by bulk download of large encrypted files from resources such as EGA. A key goal for WP9 is to enhance the ELIXIR human data access API to enable new secure data access patterns that will:

- Enable human consented 'omic' datasets to be integrated and displayed in third part community portals from the federated controlled access database (Task 9.2)
- Enable new access patterns for human data, e.g. stream data into cloud environments, access data for specific genomic loci by avoiding large file download when only a subset of data is required (Task 9.3)
- Adopt community API standards for data access to ensure interoperability with downstream tool chains and other infrastructures (Task 9.3)

The heterogeneity of jurisdictions and national infrastructures in Europe mirrors the challenges faced by the global human data research sharing community. The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) was formed as a policy-framing and technical standards setting organisation, akin to the W3C, to support the development of interoperable standards for discovering, sharing, accessing, and storing genomic data. Engagement of WP9 partners with the GA4GH working groups ensures that any standards or APIs developed in WP9 will be interoperable with emerging global standards.

Sending genomic data over networks has largely been achieved by transporting files in these well-established formats using network protocols such as FTP/HTTP(s), Globus², and proprietary protocols such as Aspera³. Commonly used tools such as Samtools⁴, GATK⁵, bedtools⁶, and IGV⁷ all support obtaining data over FTP/HTTP(s). Utilising open and widely implemented transfer protocols has ensured easy integration with common networking software libraries, reduced dependency on proprietary software or frameworks, and interoperability across network infrastructures. This file-centric approach to defining and delivering data has substantial drawbacks, however, and there is an increasing consensus that more fine-grained and flexible data access methods are needed. Several such methods of storing and serving genomic data, such as GEMINI⁸, BGT⁹, and Hail¹⁰ have been developed. To avoid fragmentation and to promote a diverse ecosystem of interoperable storage and presentation technologies for genomic data, we need to develop community standardised APIs for the discovery and delivery of read and variant data.

² Allcock *et al.* (2005) The Globus Striped GridFTP Framework and Server, <https://doi.org/10.1109/sc.2005.72>

³ <http://asperasoft.com/>

⁴ <http://www.htslib.org/>

⁵ <https://software.broadinstitute.org/gatk/>

⁶ <http://bedtools.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁷ <https://software.broadinstitute.org/software/igv/>

⁸ <http://gemini.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁹ <https://academic.oup.com/bioinformatics/article-abstract/32/4/590/1743991>

¹⁰ <https://hail.is/index.html>

EGA Data Distribution API

Secure transfer of controlled access human data is a fundamental goal of WP9. Figure 1 shows the EGA data distribution infrastructure that was developed during the EXCELERATE project (M1-36). EGA data is stored at EMBL-EBI and CRG, and can be independently distributed to users from both sites. All data is encrypted during transport by either https or pre-encrypted before being sent over unsecured connections.

Figure 1: The EGA data distribution API including secure file and streaming into local and cloud environments.

Htsget

A key goal of EXCELERATE WP9 is to develop standardised APIs for requesting and securely transferring human genetic data to a variety of downstream use-cases (Task 9.2). The htsget API^{11,12} is a standardised interface for requesting and transferring genomic data that is not bound by file semantics. Htsget enables look up of read and variant data by genomic locus, avoiding the need for users to download whole large files just to access a small fraction of the data. Additionally, it provides a mechanism for splitting large downloads into smaller chunks, enabling clients to easily implement automatic resume functionality.

The htsget protocol functions by the client providing a URL (determined via another discovery service), a preferred format, and an optional genomic range via a HTTP(s) GET

¹¹ <http://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/htsgget.html>

¹² Kelleher *et al.* (2018) *Bioinformatics*, bty492, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty492>

request (Figure 2). The server returns a small JSON block with a list of URLs. The client downloads the data from the URLs, concatenates the downloaded data in the order provided by the server to produce the full result of their query. For example, one driving use-case is to enable users to inspect genomic slices of read datasets archived at EGA in real-time into a genome browser (e.g. Integrated Genome Viewer, IGV).

Figure 1: Schematic of htsgget protocol.

The EGA data access API now supports the htsgget protocol. A recent demonstration at the GA4GH plenary meeting (October 2017) showed human data being streamed from DNAnexus¹³ and EGA into a cloud environment to carry out joint variation calling of data held at different infrastructures¹⁴. In a recent ELIXIR implementation study¹⁵, the EGA and RD-Connect collaborated to implement htsgget in the RD-Connect platform so that users could browse the raw data (archived at the EGA) supporting genetic variants (Task 9.2, Figure 2). The RD-Connect platform connects rare-disease researchers, clinicians, and bioinformatics resources.

¹³ <https://www.dnanexus.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZMYywQfvVvE&feature=youtu.be>

¹⁵ Draft final report:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1FuXZrs1nIQKBK8Hbc-eny1x5njL6V0Tw1WX26D7T1bo/edit?usp=sharing>

Figure 2: Workflow of data submission, analysis, archival, and real-time streaming of data from EGA into the RD-Connect platform.

Filesystem in User Space (FUSE)

Datasets in the EGA often consist of large collections of data files, which can consist of thousands of files that are hundreds of GB in size. The goal of task 9.3.1 is to enable ELIXIR partner services to create local mirrors of EGA datasets that can be accessed by authorised users. Within EXCELERATE WPs 4+9, a use case has been designed in cooperation with CSC Finland to cache EGA data for access by authorized users within the secure ePouta infrastructure. EGA data is temporarily cached in a local secure staging area; the EGA Data API is then deployed locally with the cache as archive back end, to allow users in the ePouta infrastructure to run FUSE layers and access the data directly from the shared cache, subject to Central EGA data access permissions.

Task 9.3 provides enhanced data access APIs by adding support for large scale data mirroring services. The Filesystem in User Space (FUSE) is a way to create a virtual local filesystem to remote data that integrates with the local computer operating system. Whereas htsget attempts to standardise data access at the API level, FUSE enables

users to access EGA datasets as if the data is hosted locally thus enabling integration with almost any downstream application (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Schematic of EGA user FUSE filesystem.

Access Management

This core goal of this WP is to deliver ELIXIR workflow for long term archive and re-use of human data consented for biomedical research requiring access-control based on data access agreements and approval process. Access to human datasets is typically controlled by a Data Access Committee (DAC) to ensure data use is consistent with participant consent agreements. The access workflow implemented in WP9 supports data submitters and ELIXIR Node coordination on data deposition into the EGA archive in a manner that will maintain data ownership in the hands of the original research data owner, and enable data release to authorised individual researchers. A user who requires access to a dataset at EGA must apply to the local DAC to gain access to a dataset. The DAC will define the Data Access Agreement, and terms of use, to which the user must agree before gaining access to the dataset. Once the user has signed the Data Access Agreement and terms of use, the DAC informs EGA of their decision so EGA can grant access to the dataset. Currently there are two methods a DAC may inform the EGA of a data access decision, either via the EGA Helpdesk or via a secure website (DAC Admin tools) where the DAC can apply the required permissions themselves. This website is only accessible via a Virtual Private Network (VPN) and requires two-factor authentication. However, the process of requesting and granting access to EGA datasets has been a notable bottleneck to human data sharing. Fundamental to the problem is the lack of automation at key stages, such as researcher authentication, and lack of an Permissions API for DACs to integrate with local systems.

Figure 4: Data access at EGA using Data Access Committees (DACs)

In Task 9.2.2, the EGA has implemented a Permissions API which allows authenticated users to query their dataset permissions. DACs and other users, authenticated via 2-factor authentication, can administer permissions of datasets they are entitled to. To allow for the use-case of Cloud access to EGA data, where datasets may not be authorised to be processed within a particular cloud instance, for example due to Ethical, Legal, and Societal Issues (ELSI), an additional type of permission has been implemented which tracks if a dataset can be mirrored and processed in one of a set of authorised cloud instances. This permission is distinct from the ELIXIR AAI as it is based on the cloud provider or location as opposed to the individual who has access to the data. The permissions API is hosted centrally at EGA ensuring that permissions are consistent throughout the federated system. A query for current permissions is done via a GET request for a user authenticated via ID token while permissions application is done via an encrypted and signed POST request.

ELIXIR Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI)

Across the ELIXIR network, we are seeing the emergence of a suite of services to support biological sciences. For human data, integration with the ELIXIR AAI¹⁶ system provides the infrastructure to be able to manage multiple different applications to different datasets across ELIXIR resources, which will form the basis for having a Europe wide system of federated identity for accessing human data resources. For example, a user with an ELIXIR account would be able to login to the EGA and RD-Connect platform to combine carry out a joint rare variant analysis using data from both resources.

As a result of WP9, ELIXIR identities now can be linked to existing EGA user accounts by the user authenticating simultaneously to ELIXIR and to EGA, and then make a REST call to the Central EGA API. Upon successful validation of both tokens the ELIXIR and EGA account identifiers are linked at Central EGA. From that point on a user can access the EGA Data API with a valid ELIXIR issued identity token. For users who have linked EGA and ELIXIR identities, the ELIXIR AAI has also introduced a new scope: if a user requests the scope 'EGA' when authenticating in ELIXIR, the ELIXIR AAI makes a REST call to Central EGA to obtain that user's EGA permissions and adds them as payload to the ELIXIR JWT token. This payload is signed by EGA, so that the EGA Data API can later validate the integrity of that payload.

Resource Entitlement Management System

The Resource Entitlement Management Systems¹⁷ (REMS) is a web-portal which builds on the EGA Access API to enable DACs to administer permissions to datasets and researchers to apply for access to datasets. The ELIXIR AAI REMS allows users to administer permissions and/or request access to datasets held at different ELIXIR nodes. REMS will list existing access rights to datasets across different repositories. This provides the DAC with a single point of administration for datasets in EGA and other archives.

¹⁶ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/services/aai>

¹⁷ <https://rems.elixir-finland.org/>

Figure 4: Example workflow of applying for, and accessing, data from the EGA in a cloud environment via REMS and a FUSE layer.

REMS uses the permissions API to query and update permissions at EGA, and uses the same underlying ELIXIR identity irrespective of whether the user is a DAC or a data requestor. This removes the current requirement of having different identities depending on role, and defines a single identity to which different roles may be assigned therefore simplifying the current system of users being required to manage multiple accounts per role. An example of the full workflow from application to data analysis is given in Figure 4. A requester with an ELIXIR identity logs into REMS and makes an application to one or more datasets (1). The DAC(s) are notified of the request, and can log into REMS to review and approve or deny the request (2). The corresponding archive (e.g. EGA) is then notified of the updated permissions (3), and the requester is informed of the DACs decision (4). The requestor can then access these data, for example by logging into a secure cloud, such as ePouta, and instantiating a virtual machine (VM) to perform an analysis (5). The request for data requires the permissions for both the requester and the cloud provider and location are checked with the source archive (6), and if authorised the data can be accessed via the EGA Data Access API (7, Figure 2). In this case a FUSE layer mounted is mounted on a cloud VM making the data appear as if it existed local to the VM (8, Figure 3).

Conclusion and Future

Tasks 9.2 and 9.3 of the EXCELERATE focus on the development of new data access patterns for sharing human genetic data in Europe. This deliverable reports on the

expansion of the EGA data access API to contribute to the development and implementation of the htsgget streaming API (Task 9.3.3), integration of EGA data into project portals (e.g. RD-Connect) (Task 9.2.1), and the implementation of a remote FUSE interface which enables local caches of EGA datasets (Task 9.3.1 and 9.3.2). The development of the EGA permissions API and integration to REMs has enabled DACs to administer permissions to datasets across the ELIXIR network including the EGA (Task 9.2.2).

The main goal of Task 9.1.2 is to create a portable submission toolkit (aka the Local EGA) that enables datasets that are subject to jurisdictional restrictions meaning they cannot be exported to the EGA to be archived and shared locally. The Local EGA project aims to build the technical implementation of the core functionality to establish a EGA instance (e.g. data submission, transformation, secure archiving, AAI integration, and data access APIs). In the remaining grant period, we will focus on adding the Data Access APIs presented in this deliverable with the Local EGA (Task 9.2.1).

In Task 9.2.2 (improved support for access management workflows within ELIXIR human data), EGA has demonstrated compatibility with REMS version 1 developed by partner CSC. EGA is working to develop the permissions API to be compatible with the version 2 of REMS, which brings an improved workflow and interactive user interface. EGA has started to perform user experience testing of REMS with a subset of DACs, who use the DAC Admin tools, and these results are being used to inform developments in version 2 of REMS and the permissions API, to try and ensure the maximum uptake of REMS as a permissions management system for EGA DACs. Additionally REMS V2 ceases to use signed and encrypted XML objects for applying permissions and uses JSON which will improve scalability and interoperability.